

Implementation of ICON 10km global coupled demonstrator and performance analysis

Deliverable D2.12

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme
under Grant Agreement No 675191

About this document

Work package in charge: WP2 Scalability

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 27 February 2019

Dissemination level: the general public (PU)

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

We have evaluated and improved the performance of a 5km-5km coupled ocean-atmosphere ICON set up. The set up makes use of ECHAM physics for the atmosphere component, but abstains from parameterisations for convection and gravity waves.

The work was accomplished to enable simulations on bigger node counts, and column-blocking parameter tuning was carried out. Throughput on O(500) nodes suggests a performance of ca. 20 simulated days per day.

Although the provided investigations are rather preliminary results than the end of the story on performance investigation for coupled high-resolution ICON simulations, the measured throughput rate is expected to already enable the investigation of selected science cases in the near future. Besides, the technical and modelling achievement lies in the fact that a 5km-5km coupled simulation could successfully be established.

Yet, more work is required to enable simulations on even bigger node counts, that is beyond 550 nodes on the supercomputer Mistral.

2. Conclusion & Results

- Investigated performance of 5km-5km coupled ICON simulation
- Carried out parameter tuning to improve performance
- Conducted scalability tests for the 5km-5km coupled setup, which suggest a throughput of ca. 20 SDPD on 500 nodes of the supercomputer Mistral, partition compute2

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of
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	this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Together with the deliverables D2.8 and D2.9 on global 1km atmosphere-only demonstrators, the deliverables D2.11 and D2.12 were meant to shed light on the computability of coupled atmosphere-ocean set ups at very high-resolution. Their analysis *“will provide valuable input for estimates of performance, scalability and limits of computability. This will be of great value for deriving the technical and organisational requirements for the operational production of predictions with coupled model ensembles at 1 km resolution in both atmosphere and ocean. The results of the analysis will build the basis for a roadmap to the implementation of an ensemble of ESMs resolving clouds and small scale eddies”* (ESiWACE DoA).

Although this deliverable aimed at the set up of a 10km-10km coupled simulation, latest ICON developments carried out by, in particular, partner MPI-M suggested the possibility to even run and execute 5km-5km coupled simulations. This already corresponds to a significant achievement and insight. Therefore, it was decided to use a respective 5km-5km set up, provided by MPI-M, for the demonstrator investigations.

The set up, named DYAMOND++ after the corresponding atmosphere-only DYAMOND runs, makes use of ECHAM physics in the atmosphere and includes parameterisations for radiation, cloud cover and microphysics, vertical diffusion and the land surface [GIO18]; the parameterisations for convection and gravity waves are not used. For the ocean component, the incompressible hydrostatic Navier-Stokes equations are solved, see [KOR17] for details.

Both ocean and atmosphere components are executed on matching 5km (ICON nomenclature: R2B9) grids. The atmosphere is discretised by 70 vertical levels, the ocean by 128 levels. Several outputs can be enabled through the set up; yet, output was restricted to atmospheric data only. More I/O is expected to come at additional cost; however, from observations in previous atmosphere-only-type simulations, it is expected that this will particularly become an issue at even higher node counts than presented in the following.

Several issues were encountered, executing DYAMOND++ on the target platform Mistral at DKRZ, including both physical and technical ones. For example, in an early phase, negative humidity values in the upper atmosphere occurred and needed to be fixed by MPI-M, and reproducibility of performance was problematic due to hardware-related issues (in particular network congestion, including broken Infiniband cables and significant other network traffic that slowed down the actual DYAMOND++ runs) that could be tracked down at last. Finally, this led to first DYAMOND++ simulations, executed on 300 (atmosphere/atm) + 120 (ocean/oce) = 420 compute nodes of the partition compute2 of Mistral. Figure 1 shows two visualisations of the corresponding simulation after four simulated days.

A demonstrator set up was derived from this DYAMOND++ set up, simulating one day in various configurations. We measured the throughput in terms of simulated days per compute day (SDPD); numbers reported in the following are based on the total elapsed time of the simulation and thus include the initialisation phase. The actual throughput will therefore be even higher. The performance of the “baseline” set up of the demonstrator was measured and resulted in 15.6 SDPD.

Several runs and configurations are listed in Table 1 and are described in the following.

Nodes	Nodes (atm)	Nodes (oce)	Notes	SDPD
420	300	120	Baseline	15.6
420	300	120	nproma=32	16.4
250	150	100	Min. setup	9.8
550	450	100	Add. HCOLL opt.	15.1
420	300	120	Add. HCOLL opt.	14.5
500	400	100	Best throughput	19.4

Table 1: Configurations of the 5km-5km coupled DYAMOND++ set up. The columns Nodes/Nodes (atm)/ Nodes (oce) correspond to the total number of compute nodes/the number of compute nodes used by the atmospheric component/the number of compute nodes used by the ocean component. The column Notes points at the actual goal/feature of the configuration compared to the baseline run. SDPD denotes the throughput in terms of simulated days per day.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Visualisation of cloud water after four days of running the DYAMOND++ 5km-5km coupled set up. (a) Global view. (b) Zoom into the Carribean sea. Courtesy by Niklas Röber, DKRZ.

A first study aimed at determining optimal values for the column-blocking parameter n_{proma} in ICON. A value $n_{\text{proma}}=32$ was found to be a good choice for both ocean and atmosphere component and led to 16.4 SDPD.

A second study investigated the memory requirements of the set up. The minimum number of required compute nodes was determined as $150 \text{ (atm)} + 100 \text{ (oce)} = 250$ compute nodes, yielding a throughput of 9.8 SDPD.

Finally, the goal was to scale the set up on higher node counts. However, issues were encountered with regard to the instantiation of MPI communicators/communication in the coupled set up. For slightly larger node counts, that is for up to 550 nodes, the issue could be resolved by adding further HCOLL options, which however also results in a significant performance penalty (throughput: 15.1 SDPD). The best performance in terms of throughput was achieved on 500 nodes abstaining from the HCOLL options, with the set up running at 19.4 SDPD. Yet, all the reported numbers are rather preliminary since many more investigations are planned and required in the future to resolve the limitations at larger node counts and to improve performance in these cases.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- [GIO18] Giorgetta, M., Brokopf, R., Crueger, T., Esch, M., Fiedler, S., Helmert, J., Hohenegger, C., Kornblueh, L., Köhler, M., Manzini, E., Mauritsen, T., Nam, C., Raddatz, T., Rast, S., Reinert, D., Sakradzija, M., Schmidt, H., Schneck, R., Schnur, R., Silvers, L., Wan, H., Zängl, G. and Stevens, B.: *ICON-A: the atmospheric component of the ICON Earth System Model. Part I: Model description*. *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.* 10: 1613-1637, 2018.
- [KOR17] Korn, P.: *Formulation of an unstructured grid model for global ocean dynamics*. *J. Comput. Phys.*, 339: 525-552, 2017

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU).

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

Sharing of materials with the general public (mostly scientists) and for audiences beyond the ESIWACE is planned at the following conferences in 2019: EGU 2019, PASC 2019, and ISC2019.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Both technical and physical issues were encountered when carrying out the presented work, see Section 4. Yet, some performance investigations could be carried out for the demonstrator.

In contrast to the goal of considering a coupled 10km-10km set up, it was possible to even go beyond that goal by considering a 5km-5km set up.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Issues on reproducibility of performance, as reported in Section 4, are expected to become an even more severe issue on upcoming exascale machines. This needs to be taken into account in future works.

To resolve these issues, such as the ones that hindered the execution on more than 500 nodes, it might be easier to rely on benchmarks for testing, which will be one target of investigation in the recently launched project ESIWACE2 (H2020). Yet, it will require even more than simplified component excerpts as benchmarks to cope with complex issues such as the reported one which only showed up at first glance in a fully coupled set up. A combination of normal and integrated benchmarks, which is similar to the differentiation of unit and integration tests, might be one way to address this topic.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The deliverable D2.11 describes developments of a coupled 10km-10km demonstrator, which is based on the community model EC-Earth.